

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 63(2) (2025) 121-146

EISSN 2543-5426

Exposure and Health Risk Evaluation of Heavy Metals in Soils Along Major Roads in Enugu State, Nigeria

Amarachukwu Rebecca Nnamani^{1,*} and Akudu Adaobi Ukamaka²

¹ Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu, Nigeria

² Department of Chemistry, Renaissance University, Ugbawka, Enugu, Nigeria

*E-mail address: nnamanirebecca94@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the concentrations and potential health risks of selected heavy metals (Lead (Pb), Manganese (Mn), Nickel (Ni), Copper (Cu), Chromium (Cr), Arsenic (As), Mercury (Hg) and Iron (Fe)) in surface soils (0-5 cm) from three major urban roads in Enugu State, Nigeria. Composite soil samples were collected, acid-digested and analysed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry. Contamination levels were assessed through four pollution indices; Geoaccumulation index (Igeo), Contamination Factor (CF), Pollution Load Index (PLI) and Enrichment Factor (EF) while human health risk was evaluated using United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) models considering ingestion, dermal contact and inhalation pathways for both adults and children. Results indicate that concentrations of some metals particularly As were slightly elevated compared to background values. The pollution indices showed low to moderate level of contamination in all the three urban roads except for As with PLI value greater than 1 ($PLI > 1$) in the commercial road indicating slightly nature of contamination. The assessment of health risk indicated that there were mainly three exposure pathways for people via ingestion, dermal contact and inhalation. The main exposure pathway of heavy metals for both children and adults is ingestion. The values of Hazard Quotients (HQ) and Hazard Index (HI) for all the heavy metals and exposure pathways were < 1 , indicating no significant non-carcinogenic health risk. Meanwhile, the HI values for children were higher than that for adults indicating that children have higher potential health risk than adults. Cancer Risk (CR) values for Cr, As, Pb and Ni were within the acceptable risk range (10^{-6} - 10^{-4}) showing negligible carcinogenic risk. The order of exposure were observed to be adults $<$ children. Though the CR and TCR results were observed to be within the acceptable range for developing cancer, the result however suggest that children could be more

susceptible to potential carcinogenic risk following continual exposure to heavy metals from vehicular activity. This leads to a concern about the expansion of unregulated settlements along heavy traffic roads in Enugu State, Nigeria. It is recommended that continuous periodic monitoring should be done to track potential changes due to increasing traffic and urbanization in the state.

Keywords: Roadside soil contamination, heavy metals, human health risk assessment, average daily intake, hazard quotient, hazard index, cancer risk index

1. INTRODUCTION

For the past few decades, heavy metal contaminations of typical urban road soils continue to attract a great concern from public and also environmental researchers in the worldwide, due to their toxicity and close relationship with the human health (Adimalla and Wang, 2018; Khademi *et al.*, 2019). The rapid urbanization and developments, expansion of industrial sectors and increasing vehicle emissions have largely led to heavy metal contaminations of urban roadside soils. And the improved standard of living had also led to high number of vehicles in the city. Most of these vehicles are imported into the country and they can be described as second hand and fairly used with low internal fuel combustion efficiency and some other problems. Heavy metals in soils from urban roadside can accumulate in the human body via direct inhalation, ingestion and dermal contact absorption (Poggio *et al.*, 2008). According to numerous studies, the anthropogenic source of heavy metal pollution is considered to be the main factor for environmental pollution issues, especially in urban areas (Adimalla and Wang, 2018).

In urban soil, heavy metals can be present in both natural and anthropogenic forms. The natural forms of heavy metals due to the weathering of rock minerals are present at relatively low concentrations (Dakane, 2012). Predominantly, human activities have a major cause for the enrichment of heavy metals in the urban soils such as vehicle traffic, industrial, irrigation activities, and also mining activities (Keshav Krishna and Rama Mohan, 2016).

The road anthropogenic sources of heavy metals include traffic emission, fuel burning in the engine, vehicle exhaust particles, tire wear particles, weathered street surface particles, industrial emission from power plants, coal combustion, metallurgical industry, auto repair shop, chemical plant, domestic emission, weathering of buildings and pavement surfaces, deposited from the atmosphere and so on (Wei *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, studying the chemical properties of urban roadside soil gives the opportunity to evaluate the urban environment quality, as well as its relation to human health. Heavy metals can be transferred to soils and accumulated plants, animals, water bodies and finally entered into the human body through a wide range of food chain (Zhao *et al.*, 2019), resulting in an acute threat to human health.

Many studies have been performed on heavy metal pollution of soil around the world (Wei and Yang, 2010). However, there are limited studies about heavy metals of soil in major roads of Enugu state, Nigeria. This study indicates the heavy metal pollution in three urban roads in Enugu city. In order to evaluate the potential human health risk, the study utilizes the methodology, developed by the Environmental Protection Agency of United States (US EPA) and estimated non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risk via eight heavy metals (Pb, Mn, Ni, Cu, Cr, As, Hg and Fe) for children and adults, separately. This study aims to determine the concentrations level of Lead, Manganese, Nickel, Copper, Chromium, Arsenic, Mercury and

Iron in roadside soil samples of different traffic road categories and to evaluate their potential risks to the human health.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The study area is Enugu, the capital of Enugu State, Nigeria. The city of Enugu is made up of three Local Government Areas (LGAs) Enugu East, North and South LGAs. The city lies approximately between latitude 6°21'N and 6°30'N and between longitude 7°26'E and 7°37'E of the Equator and Greenwich Meridian respectively.

Fig. 1. Map of Enugu City showing Agbani Road, Ogui New Layout and Enugu/PH expressway (Source: Google maps: www.igooglemaps.com)

It is bounded in the east by Nkanu LGA, in the West by Udi LGA, in the North by Igbo-Etiti and Isiuzor and in the south by Nkanu West LGA. “It lies on the plains close to the foot of the east facing escarpment of Enugu-Awgu Cuesta” (Okoye, 1975). It has a total area of 612 square kilometers with a population of 722,664 individuals according to 2006 census (National Population Commission, 2007).

It records a lot of transportation activities due to high population density, industrialization and commercial businesses in the city. Although a rail track passed through the city but the major means of transportation is by road and vehicles of all sorts including motorcycle, tricycle, mini bus, trucks, commuters, taxi and private cars are used. A significant number of people walk on the roadside depending on their destinations and hawking activities. Automobile repair workshops, welding and metal construction works by the roadside are common phenomena in the major urban roads of the state. Through these activities, heavy metal pollutants are emitted into the atmosphere and deposited in the roadside soil.

2. 2. Sampling and preparation

For the study, fifteen road soil samples were collected from three major traffic roads of Enugu South LGA, Enugu state. At each sampling road, three subsamples were taken from each side of the road at variable distances of 100m, 200m and 300m away from the edge of the road, thoroughly mixed to form one composite sample, and then placed into a zip-locked polyethylene bags. Samples were collected from December, 2024 to April, 2025 to avoid rain-washing out the heavy metals. The respective sample points are Enugu/PH express road, Agbani road and Ogui new layout road. Soil samples were pretreated and processed according to the method described by Alexander *et al.* (2015). The elemental concentrations of the digested soil samples were carried out using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) Agilent FS240AA Model.

2. 3. Sample Digestion Procedure

The collected soil samples were air-dried to constant weight and sieved through a stainless mesh wire. Portions of two gram of each of each air-dried dust sample were ashed in a muffle furnace at 460 °C for 12 hours. The ash were digested in 20 ml freshly prepared aqua-regia (1:3 HNO₃ : HCl) on a hot plate for 3 hrs (Praveena *et al.*, 2015). After the digestion, the digests were first centrifuged and were acid washed to pass through whatman 540 filter paper and then filtered into 100 ml volumetric flask then made up to the volume with distilled water. Calibration standards were prepared from the stock solution of the elements to be determined by serial dilution and were matrix matched with the acid concentration of the digested samples (Radojevic and Bashkin, 2006). The digested samples were then analyzed for heavy metal using computerized Agilent FS240AA Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. All the measurements were in duplicate analyses. Statistical analysis of mean and standard deviation were obtained, using a Microsoft Excel 2007 spreadsheet as recommended by (Gary, 2004).

2. 4. Pollution assessment method

Pollution indices were adopted to estimate the heavy metals pollution in the soils of the three urban roads in Enugu sate. In this study the following indices; geo-accumulation index, contamination factor, pollution load index and enrichment factor were employed to measure the extent of pollution.

2. 4. 1. Geo-accumulation Index (Igeo)

Geo-accumulation Index was proposed by (Muller, 1969). In this study, Igeo was used to identify whether the road soil in three urban roads were polluted by heavy metals and quantify the degree of the contamination. Igeo was calculated by:

$$I_{geo} = \log_2 \frac{C_n}{1.5B_n} \quad (1)$$

where: C_n metal is the measured concentration of the examined heavy metal in the soil sample and B_n is the geochemical background concentration or reference value of the metal n . The factor 1.5 is introduced to minimize the effect of possible variations in the background or control values which may be attributed to lithogenic variation in the soil. The background values used were reference values of metals by DPR (2002), for maximum allowable concentration of the metals in Nigeria soil ($As = 1$, $Cr = 100$, $Ni = 35$, $Pb = 85$, $Cu = 36$, $Fe = 5000$, $Mn = 850$, $Hg = 3$) in mg/kg.

Seven contamination classes are used to define the degree of metal pollutants in soils based on the increasing value of the index of geoaccumulation as follows: $I_{geo} < 0$ means unpolluted; $0 \leq I_{geo} < 1$ means unpolluted to moderately polluted; $1 \leq I_{geo} < 2$ means moderately polluted; $2 \leq I_{geo} < 3$ means moderately to strongly polluted; $3 \leq I_{geo} < 4$ means strongly polluted; $4 \leq I_{geo} < 5$ means strongly to very strongly polluted; $I_{geo} > 5$ means very strongly polluted (Huu *et al.*, 2010).

2. 4. 2. Contamination Factor (CF)

The contamination factor is a major tool for identifying the pollution and the contamination level in the environmental matrix. The level of contamination of the roadside soil by the heavy metal was expressed in terms of a Contamination Factor (CF) and determined by employing the model by Lacatusu, (2000).

$$CF = \frac{\text{concentration of the metals in soil}}{\text{Target (background values)}} \quad (2)$$

The following contamination classes were used to define the contamination factor; $CF < 1$ refers to low contamination; $1 \leq CF < 3$ means moderate contamination; $3 \leq CF \leq 6$ indicates considerable contamination and $CF > 6$ indicates very high contamination

2. 4. 3. Pollution Load Index (PLI)

Pollution Load Index (PLI) can be defined as the sum of contamination factor. According to Daud *et al.* (2009), PLI is considered as a combined tool used to assess the amount of pollution at a site for a particular set of heavy metals.

The pollution load index (PLI) was developed by Thomilson *et al.* (1980), as follows;

$$PLI = (C_{f1} \times C_{f2} \times C_{f3} \times C_{f4} \dots \dots C_{fn})^{1/n} \quad (3)$$

where: n is the number of metals studied and C_f is the contamination factor calculated as described in Equation 1. The PLI gives an estimate of the metal concentration status. The ranks

of values of $PLI < 1$ denote perfection: $PLI = 1$ present that only baseline levels of the pollutants are present and $PLI > 1$ would indicate deterioration of site quality

2. 4. 4. Enrichment Factor (EF)

Enrichment factor (EF) has been widely used to differentiate anthropogenic and natural sources of trace elements in soils (Lu *et al.*, 2009). The EF for individual metal was estimated to examine the impact of human-induced activities on heavy metals in soils as shown below:

$$Ef = \frac{(Cn(\text{sample})/Cref(\text{sample}))}{Bn(\text{background})/Bref(\text{background})} \quad (4)$$

where: Cn (Sample) is the concentration of the given element in the examined environment, and $Cref$ (Sample) is the concentration of the element in the reference sample. Bn (Background) is the concentration of the element in the background samples in the environment. $Bref$ (Background) is the concentration of the element in the reference background sample environment. In this study, Fe was used as the reference value element as it the most naturally abundant element in the soil. A value of EF close to 1 indicates a crustal origin, whereas those EF values >10 indicates a non-crustal source (Wang *et al.*, 2005).

Five contamination categories are recognized on the basis of the enrichment factor as follows. $EF < 2$ is deficiency to minimal enrichment, $EF 2 - 5$ is moderate enrichment, $EF 5 - 20$ is significant enrichment, $EF 20 - 40$ is very high enrichment, $EF > 40$ is extremely high enrichment. As the EF values increase, the contributions of the anthropogenic origins also increases

2. 5. Human health risk assessment model

Health risk assessment models were used to quantify the health risk (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) for children and adults exposed to heavy metals in road dust. They are based on those developed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2009; USEPA, 2002)

Local residents are exposed to metals in road dust through three main exposure pathways: direct ingestion, inhalation through mouth and nose, and dermal absorption. The total non-carcinogenic risk was calculated for each metal in road dust by the summation of the individual risks calculated for the three exposure pathways (USEPA, 2002). The average daily intake (ADI) ($\text{mg kg}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$) for heavy metals in road dust through the three exposure pathways was calculated according to Exposure Factors Handbook (USEPA, 2009) and the Technical Report of USEPA (USEPA, 2009) using the following equations

2. 5. 1. Average daily intake (ADI) (mg/kg/day) of heavy metals in soil media

$$ADI - \text{ingestion} = \left(\frac{CS \times IR_{\text{ing}} \times EF \times ED \times TR}{BW \times AT} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$ADI - \text{inhalation} = \left(\frac{CS \times IR_{\text{inh}} \times EF \times ED}{PEF \times BW \times AT} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$ADI - \text{dermal} = \left(\frac{CS \times AF \times SA \times DAF \times EF \times ED \times TR}{BW \times AT} \right) \quad (7)$$

where: AD_{ingestion}, AD_{inhalation}, and AD_{dermal} are the average daily intake or amount of exposure to heavy metals (mg (kg day)⁻¹) via ingestion or oral intake, inhalation and dermal contacts, respectively. Cs is the concentration of the heavy metals in soil (mg kg⁻¹); IR_{ing} is the ingestion rate (mg day⁻¹); EF is the exposure frequency of the people (day year⁻¹); ED is the exposure duration (years); TR is the conversion factor in kg/mg, IR_{inh} is the inhalation rate (m³ day⁻¹); EF is the particulate emission factors (m³ kg⁻¹); SA is the skin surface area (cm²); AF is the skin adherence factor (mg cm⁻²); DAF is the dermal absorption factor; BW and AT are the body weight (kg) and average exposed time (years), respectively (USEPA, 2009; USEPA, 2002).

The detailed description of the values of exposure factors for children and adults applied to the above models (Equations 5-7) are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Definition and reference value of some parameters for health risk assessment of heavy metal.

Indicators	Parameters	Definition	Units	Adult	Children	References
Exposure factors	EF	Exposure frequency	days year ⁻¹	350	350	USEPA (2002)
	ED	Exposure duration	years	30	6	USEPA (2002)
	BW	Body weight	kg	70	20	USEPA (2002)
	TR	Conversion factor	mg kg ⁻¹	1 × 10 ⁶	1 × 10 ⁶	
	Cs	Concentration of heavy metals	mg kg ⁻¹	-	-	present study
	IR _w	daily water ingestion rate	L/day	2.5 L/day	0.78 L/day	USEPA (2002)
Ingestion	IR _{ing}	Ingestion rate	mg day ⁻¹	100	200	USEPA (2002)
Inhalation	IR _{inh}	Inhalation rate	m ³ day ⁻¹	20	10	USEPA (2009)
	PEF	Particle emission factor	m ³ kg ⁻¹	1.36 × 10 ⁹	1.36 × 10 ⁹	USEPA (2009)
Skin contact	SA	Exposed skin surface area	cm ²	5800	2100	USEPA (2002)
	AF	Skin adherence factor	mg cm ²	0.7	0.2	USEPA (2002)
	DAF	Dermal absorption factor	-	0.1	0.1	USEPA (2002)
	AT	Average time Carcinogens Non-carcinogens	days year ⁻¹	70 × 365 ED × 365	70 × 365 ED × 365	USEPA (2002)

2. 5. 2. Non-carcinogenic risk assessment

Reference dose (RfD) is a key factor to estimate the non-carcinogenic health risk of a single heavy metal which is traditionally characterized by the hazard quotient (HQ). Therefore, HQ is computed as the ratio of the average daily dose (ADD) and a reference dose (RfD).

The equation of HQ is defined as follows (USEPA, 2002):

$$HQ = \frac{ADI}{RfD} \quad (8)$$

where ADI is the average daily intake of heavy metals *n* through *e* exposed (ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact) pathways (mg (kg day)⁻¹) and RfD is the reference dose of heavy metal *n* through (ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact) pathways (mg (kg day)⁻¹). The reference dose (RfD) for the selected heavy metals is listed in Table 2.

Eventually, to assess the overall non-carcinogenic risk of six heavy metals that can be evaluated by the sum of the HQ values of multiple exposure pathways is also expressed as a hazard index (HI). The equation of HI is as follows:

$$HI = HQ_{der} + HQ_{ing} + HQ_{inh} \\ = \left(\left[\frac{ADI(Der)}{RfD} \right] + \left[\frac{ADI(ing)}{RfD} \right] + \left[\frac{ADI(inh)}{RfD} \right] \right) \quad (9)$$

where: HI = sum total of more than one hazard quotient of multiple exposure pathway, HQ = hazard quotient is a unit-less number for expressing the probability of an adverse health effect, ADI (E) = average daily intake (exposure), RfD = reference dose of heavy metals (mg/kg/day).

There is no non-carcinogenic health risk for humans if the value of HI is less than one, while if it is greater than one, it is assumed to be an adverse non-carcinogenic health risk occur (Adimalla and Wang 2018; USEPA, 2002).

2. 5. 3. Carcinogenic risk assessment

The carcinogenic risk is assessed by calculating the incremental probability of an individual developing cancer over a lifetime as a result of exposure to the potential carcinogen (Pan et al., 2018). Carcinogenic risk and total carcinogenic risks are computed using the following equation:

$$CR = ADD \times SF \quad (10)$$

$$TCR = CR_{der} + CR_{ing} + CR_{inh} \\ = \left([ADI_{ing} \times CSF] + [ADI_{inh} \times CSF] + [ADI_{derm} \times CSF] \right) \quad (11)$$

where: CR(ing), CR(inh), and CR(dermal) are risks contributions through ingestion, inhalation and dermal pathways respectively. CR is the carcinogenic risk; ADI is the average daily intake; TCR is the total carcinogenic risk; and SF is the carcinogenicity slope factor over a lifetime (mg/(kg·day)); TCR is the total excess lifetime cancer calculated from risk pathway. Carcinogenic risk values ranging from 1×10^{-6} to 1×10^{-4} are typically considered as a safe limit for human health while carcinogenic risk value exceeds the limit of 1×10^{-4} results to a

lifetime cancer risk to the human body (USEPA, 2009). Both non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risk assessment of heavy metals are calculated using RfD and CSF values derived largely from USEPA as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Reference doses (RfD) in (mg/(kg·day) and Cancer Slope Factors (CSF) for the different heavy metals.

Heavy metals (mg kg ⁻¹)	Reference dose (RfD)			Slope factor (SF)		
	RfD _{Ing}	RfD _{Inh}	RfD _{dermal}	Oral SF	Inhal. SF	Dermal SF
Cu	4.00E-02	4.02E-02	1.20E-02	-	-	-
Fe	8.40E+00	2.20E-04	7.00E-02	-	-	-
Cr	3.00E-03	2.86E-05	3.00E-03	5.01E-01	4.20E+01	2.00E+01
As	3.00E-04	3.01E-04	1.23E-04	1.50E+00	4.30E-03	3.66E+00
Hg	3.00E-04	8.57E-05	2.10E-05			
Pb	3.50E-03	3.52E-03	5.25E-04	8.50E-03	4.20E-02	-
Mn	4.60E-02	1.43E-05	1.84E-03			
Ni	2.00E-02	2.06E-02	5.40E-03	1.70E+00	8.40E-01	4.25E+01

Source: <http://www.epa.gov/ncea/efh>. NA: not available

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Concentrations of heavy metals in soil samples

Table 3 shows the mean concentration of each heavy metal in soils from the three urban road sites based on the activities of the different roads. Concentrations of heavy metals in soil show significant variability. The elemental composition of the road soil revealed Fe as the most abundant in all the three urban roads with the highest mean concentration of 274.79 mg/kg, whereas Cr was the least with the mean value of 0.01 mg/kg. Mn which is an essential element is also seen to be present in moderately high concentration of in all the three roads. Intermediate in this range were As, Ni, Cu, Pb, and Hg with their highest mean concentrations of 4.00, 6.93, 11.73, 4.54, and 21.75 mg/kg respectively are also found to be in trace quantities. In a work of Abechi *et al.* (2010), it was found that Fe concentration in the roadside soil samples could be attributed to metal construction works, iron bending and welding of metals which is a common practice along the urban roads in Enugu city. The heavy metals in urban roadside soil take their origin from sources such as vehicles, road wear, activities of roadside artisans (battery charging, vehicle repairs, iron-bending, vehicle painting and panel beating) and emissions and or discharges from industries. Pb, Cr and Ni come mainly from vehicular activities such as tyre wear, wear of brake linings and studded tyres may be the sources for Ni, Cr, and Pb and Fe, Ni,

Cr and Cu respectively (Chen *et al.*, 2007). Corrosion of bushings, brake wires and radiators and the various types of deicing chemicals and friction materials used on road surfaces for slipperiness control could expose metals such Cu, Fe, Ni and Cr into the environment (Chen *et al.*, 2007).

From Table 3, Fe and Mn in soil are the two highest while other heavy metals present lower concentrations in soil and this is consistent with previous research studies on soil pollution (Chen *et al.*, 2007). It can also be noted that the concentrations of heavy metals are highest in soils from the industrial road site. Soil from commercial road contains the second highest concentrations of heavy metals while soil sample from residential area has the lowest heavy metal concentration.

Seasonally, the mean concentrations of heavy metals in (mg/kg) were found higher in hammattan season (between Dec. – Feb) than those of post-hammattan season (between March–April), except, Cr and Hg that shows insignificant concentration in both seasons. The significant increase in concentration of elements during the hammattan season could be attributed to other combustion sources in the area and thermal inversion as well as ground level fog, which cause stagnation of air and consequently the buildup of pollutants (Khare and Baruah, 2010).

Table 3. Mean concentrations and standard deviation of heavy metals (mg/kg) in roadside soil samples between December, 2024 to April, 2025 at the various roads.

	Sample /month	Cr	As	Ni	Cu	Hg	Fe	Pb	Mn
		Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD	Mean± SD
R1P1	Dec	ND	2.54± 0.19	6.93± 0.25	7.08± 0.11	ND	214.28± 3.68	2.3± 0.07	16.23± 0.14
	Jan	0.038 ±0.05	3.25± 0.14	3.13± 0.11	7.45± 0.07	0.03± 0.04	274.79± 3.20	4.16± 0.23	12.65± 0.21
	Feb	ND	3.85± 0.18	0.53± 0.04	5.96± 0.12	ND	222.81± 0.30	1.88± 0.14	8.49± 0.16
	March	0.05± 0.04	1.5± 0.11	1.15± 0.21	4.98± 0.11	ND	213.95± 1.80	1.25± 0.07	15.83± 0.14
	April	0.01± 0.02	4.00± 0.11	0.08± 0.07	7.86± 0.09	ND	245.48± 3.82	1.8± 0.11	12.18± 0.25
R2P2	Dec	ND	3.13± 0.04	4.94± 0.19	10.05± 0.04	ND	214.51± 0.76	4.54± 0.12	12.71± 0.16
	Jan	ND	3.11± 0.09	2.05± 0.04	11.73± 0.07	ND	233.65± 2.40	3.88± 0.18	17.15± 0.21
	Feb	ND	2.75± 0.25	0.25± 0.04	5.16± 0.16	ND	189.5± 3.36	2.08± 0.11	9.88± 0.18
	March	ND	3.15± 0.07	1.5± 0.11	6.85± 0.14	ND	194.98± 3.36	3.25± 1.06	6.18± 0.25
	April	0.2± 0.04	3.09± 0.12	1.44± 0.19	3.65± 0.11	ND	159.87± 6.03	4.04± 0.05	13.7+ 0.14

R3P3	Dec	ND	3.13± 0.11	1.5± 0.18	5.54± 1.89	ND	172.18± 3.22	1.05± 0.07	21.75± 0.18
	Jan	0.03± 0.04	2.39± 0.09	1.5± 0.21	3.6± 0.14	ND	157.68± 1.34	0.7± 0.07	9.75± 0.14
	Feb	ND	3.7± 0.11	0.03± 0.04	4.63± 0.18	ND	161.13± 3.64	1.38± 0.18	13.58± 0.11
	March	ND	3.23± 0.07	1.24± 0.16	3.13± 0.18	ND	189.61± 2.28	1.3± 0.07	16.05± 0.07
	April	0.13± 0.04	1.48± 0.11	0.45± 0.11	4.6± 0.11	ND	138.06± 1.50	0.58± 0.11	11.2± 0.07

All values represent mean±SD (Standard Deviation). ND: Not Detected; RIPI = Enugu/PH express road; R2P2 = Agbani road; R3P3 = Ogui new layout road.

3. 2. Evaluation of metals pollution using pollution indices

The assessment of the environmental pollution of the study area based on pollution assessment indices such as geochemical-accumulation index (*I_{geo}*), contamination factor (CF), pollution load index (PLI) and enrichment factor (EF) were presented in (Table 4, 5, 6 and 7)

3.2.1. Geo accumulation index (*I_{geo}*)

The results of the geo-accumulation index of the soil samples of the three urban roads were presented in (Table 4). The *I_{geo}* values for Cu, Fe, Cr, Hg, Pb, Mn and Ni indicated low variability among the three sampling roads and were within *I_{geo}* < 0 implying that the soil samples were unpolluted. The result revealed that these metals in respect of all the studied roads fall under unpolluted range.

The calculated *I_{geo}* values for As showed that the soil samples were moderately polluted ($1 < I_{geo} \leq 2$) at all the three roads. It is imperative to emphasize that the average *I_{geo}* values for As were relatively higher than other trace metals, suggesting that the soil samples from the three urban roads must have been contaminated by As due to anthropogenic activities.

Table 4. Geo accumulation index analysis of heavy metals in road soil samples.

Geo accumulation Index									
Roads	Months	Cu	Fe	Cr	As	Hg	Pb	Mn	Ni
R1P1	Dec	-2.9321	-5.12932	-	0.75844	-	-5.7927	-6.2961	-2.92243
	Jan	-2.8576	-4.77049	-16.609	1.11547	-7.491	-4.9369	-6.6552	-4.07039
	Feb	-3.1789	-5.073	-	1.35989	-	-6.0874	-7.2309	-6.64386
	March	-3.4401	-5.13155	-11.946	0	-	-6.6724	-6.3321	-5.51261
	April	-2.779	-4.93321	-18.194	1.41507	-	-6.1463	-6.7104	-9.45121

R2P2	Dec	-2.4257	-5.12777	-	1.05889	-	-4.8124	-6.6485	-3.41046
	Jan	-2.2033	-5.00447	-	1.05311	-	-5.0401	-6.2161	-4.67862
	Feb	-3.3868	-5.30662	-	0.87446	-	-5.9412	-7.0125	-7.71425
	March	-2.9787	-5.26549	-	1.07038	-	-5.6298	-7.6898	-5.12928
	April	-3.8869	-5.55201	-10.671	1.04147	-	-4.9808	-6.5401	-5.19068
R3P3	Dec	-3.2856	-5.4449	-	1.05889	-	-6.9239	-5.8733	-5.12928
	Jan	-3.9068	-5.57182	-17.194	0.67053	-	-7.5089	-7.0308	-5.12928
	Feb	-3.5454	-5.54059	-	1.30256	-	-6.5349	-6.5534	-11.0362
	March	-4.1110	-5.30578	-	1.10433	-	-6.6158	-6.3118	-5.40682
	April	-3.5532	-5.76352	-11.466	-0.0242	-	-7.7927	-6.8308	-6.86625

R1P1 = Enugu/PH express road (Industrial road); R2P2 = Agbani road (Commercial road);
R3P3 = Ogui new layout road (residential road).

3. 2. 2. The contamination factor (CF)

Table 5 shows the results of the calculated CF values for each heavy metal in the three urban road soil samples of the investigated sites. Cf values less than 1 ($CF < 1$) and those between 1 and 3 ($1 \leq CF < 3$) are considered to pose low and moderate degree of contamination, respectively. Therefore, the results of the study at the various roads showed that the soil samples taken from Enugu/PH express road, Agbani road and Ogui new layout road were moderately contaminated by As whereas Cu, Fe, Cr, Hg, Pb, Mn and Ni indicated low degree of contamination. Arsenic could be introduced to soil, air, and aquatic environment through anthropogenic inputs such as fossil fuel combustion, application of phosphate fertilizers, insecticides and waste dumping and incineration (Suresh *et al.*, 2015).

Table 5. Contamination factor of heavy metals in road soils of three roads in Enugu state.

Contamination factor (CF)									
Roads	Months	Cu	Fe	Cr	As	Hg	Pb	Mn	Ni
R1P1	Dec	0.196527	0.042856	0	2.5375	0	0.027058824	0.019088235	0.197857143
	Jan	0.206944	0.054958	0.000015	3.25	0.0083	0.048970588	0.014882353	0.089285714
	Feb	0.165625	0.044562	0	3.85	0	0.022058824	0.009985294	0.015
	March	0.138194	0.04279	0.00038	1.5	0	0.014705882	0.018617647	0.032857143
	April	0.218402	0.049096	0.000005	4	0	0.021176471	0.014323529	0.002142857

R2P2	Dec	0.279167	0.042902	0	3.125	0	0.053382	0.014956	0.141071
	Jan	0.325694	0.04673	0	3.1125	0	0.045588	0.020176	0.058571
	Feb	0.143403	0.0379	0	2.75	0	0.024412	0.011618	0.007143
	March	0.190278	0.038996	0	3.15	0	0.030294	0.007265	0.042857
	April	0.101389	0.031972	0.00092	3.0875	0	0.0475	0.016118	0.041071
R3P3	Dec	0.153819	0.034436	0	3.125	0	0.012353	0.025588	0.042857
	Jan	0.1	0.031536	0.00001	2.3875	0	0.008235	0.011471	0.042857
	Feb	0.128472	0.032226	0	3.7	0	0.016176	0.015971	0.000714
	March	0.086806	0.037922	0	3.225	0	0.015294	0.018882	0.035357
	April	0.127778	0.027612	0.00053	1.475	0	0.006765	0.013176	0.012857

R1P1 = Enugu/PH express road (Industrial road); R2P2 = Agbani road (Commercial road);
R3P3 = Ogui new layout road (residential road).

3. 2. 3. The pollution load index (PLI)

The calculated pollution load index values of heavy metals in the three urban road soil samples of Enugu state are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Pollution load index analysis of heavy metals in road soil samples.

Pollution load index									
Sites	Indices	Cu	Fe	Cr	As	Hg	Pb	Mn	Ni
R1P1	PLI	0.34555	0.147205	0.000001	1.927470	0.008333	0.098831	0.072418	0.108107
R2P2	PLI	0.35487	0.132453	0.000920	2.004016	0.009330	0.130764	0.067091	0.133989
R3P3	PLI	0.26157	0.117626	0.000582	1.83988	0.000653	0.060102	0.076445	0.070298

R1P1 = Enugu/PH express road (Industrial road); R2P2 = Agbani road (Commercial road);
R3P3 = Ogui new layout road (residential road).

The pollution load index data (Table 6) highlights the pollution status of the soils in the three urban roads sites. Pollution load index was adopted to assess the contamination individual metals. The pollution index was calculated based on concentration of Cu, Fe, Cr, As, Hg, Pb, Mn and Ni which are considered significant in the pollution assessment of the urban road sites. The PLI values of the studied metals shows that the soil samples of the three urban roads were unpolluted, with PLI values between zero and one for all the road sites except As with PLI value greater than 1 (PLI >1) in the commercial road (R2P2) indicating the severe nature of

pollution and deterioration of the soil quality of the road site. It is observed that, the soils of these urban roads were not polluted by all the studied metals except As. The high PLI value could be attributable to the cumulative concentrations of As in that particular road, implying an alarming condition.

3. 2. 4. The Enrichment factor (EF)

The computed enrichment factor results for the three urban roads of Enugu state are shown in Tables 7.

Table 7. The enrichment factors (EF) of soil samples of three urban roads of Enugu state.

Enrichment factor (EF)									
Roads	Months	Cu	Fe	Cr	As	Hg	Pb	Mn	Ni
R1P1	Dec	3.575963059	Used as reference metal for the calculation	0	46.171	0	0.492354589	0.347324053	3.600151804
	Jan	3.765501737		0.000272936	59.136	0.1516	0.891054773	0.270795024	1.62461724
	Feb	3.013664981		0	70.053	0	0.401376024	0.181689547	0.272935696
	March	2.514546462		0.006914371	27.293	0	0.267584016	0.338761364	0.597859144
	April	3.973994283		0.000090978	72.782	0	0.385320983	0.260626832	0.038990814
R2P2	Dec	5.974035238		0	66.873	0	1.142357221	0.320061429	3.018862156
	Jan	6.969707778		0	66.606	0	0.975566773	0.431766972	1.253400997
	Feb	3.068751932		0	58.848	0	0.522400272	0.248612178	0.15285378
	March	4.071854864		0	67.408	0	0.648279855	0.155461286	0.91712268
	April	2.169674489		0.019687567	66.071	0	1.016477637	0.344910059	0.878909235
R3P3	Dec	4.877583		0	99.093	0	0.391709	0.811398	1.358991
	Jan	3.170979		0.000317	75.707	0	0.261139	0.36373	1.358991
	Feb	4.073827		0	117.32	0	0.512953	0.506424	0.02265
	March	2.752586		0	102.26	0	0.484973	0.598755	1.121168
	April	4.051807		0.016806	46.771	0	0.214507	0.417823	0.407697

RP1 = Enugu/PH express road (Industrial road); R2P2 = Agbani road (Commercial road); R3P3 = Ogui new layout road (residential road).

The enrichment level of studied heavy metals in the road soils of Enugu/PH express road, Agbani road and Ogui new layout road was from minimal to extreme level. Enrichment Factor (EF) of the heavy metals in soils showed that Cr, Pb, Mn, Ni, and Hg had minimal enrichment in all the three urban road sites (EF < 2), Cu had moderate enrichment (EF 2 – 5). While As had the maximum EF values higher than 40, (EF > 40) in the three urban roads which

illustrated the relation of metal with anthropogenic sources. The high accumulations of As in the road soil of the three urban roads showed their origin from traffic emissions (Yan *et al.*, 2018), application of phosphate fertilizers, insecticides and waste dumping and incineration (Suresh *et al.*, 2015). The pollution level of As in the studied areas of the urban roads was found significantly higher than other metals, this result connects the elevated concentration of As with artificial sources. This higher concentration of As in urban road soil can be related with the several exhaust and non-exhaust traffic emission sources such as tailpipe, brake wear, and tyre wear. An EF value of As >10 from all the three studied roads is a clear indication that traffic emissions are a major source of enrichment for these toxic metals in road site.

3. 3. Health risks assessment results

The hazard quotient (HQ) values of different exposure pathways and hazard index (HI) of the analyzed heavy metals in soil particles from the three different traffic zones are shown in Tables 8, 9, 10 and 11. Non-carcinogenic effects of soil for the selected elements were estimated for both children and adults through the exposure routes of ingestion, inhalation and dermal. The estimated average daily exposure doses (mg/(kg·day)) through ingestion, dermal contact and inhalation exposure were greater for children than for adults in the three traffic zones with the ingestion being the exposure route associated with the highest risk. The results are consistent with other earlier studies (Adimalla and Wang 2018; Diami et al. 2016).

Table 8. Non-carcinogenic health risks assessment of soil for the selected elements at Enugu/PH express road.

SOIL	Samples	ADULT			CHILDREN			HI = ΣHQ	
		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL	INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL		
Elements (mg/kg)	Months	HQ _{ING}	HQ _{INH}	HQ _{DERM}	HQ _{ING}	HQ _{INH}	HQ _{DERM}	ADULT	CHILD
Cu	Dec	2.42E-04	3.56E-08	2.00E-04	2.26E-03	8.28E-08	9.67E-04	4.42E-04	3.23E-03
	Jan	2.55E-04	3.73E-08	2.11E-04	2.38E-03	8.71E-08	1.02E-03	4.66E-04	3.40E-03
	Feb	2.04E-04	2.99E-08	1.68E-04	1.91E-03	6.97E-08	8.14E-04	3.73E-04	2.72E-03
	March	1.71E-04	2.49E-08	1.41E-04	1.59E-03	5.82E-08	6.79E-04	3.11E-04	2.27E-03
	April	2.70E-04	3.93E-08	2.23E-04	2.53E-03	9.18E-08	1.08E-03	4.93E-04	3.60E-03
Fe	Dec	3.50E-05	1.96E-04	1.04E-03	3.26E-04	4.59E-04	5.01E-03	1.27E-03	5.80E-03
	Jan	4.48E-05	2.52E-04	1.33E-03	4.18E-04	5.86E-04	6.44E-03	1.63E-03	7.45E-03
	Feb	3.63E-05	2.04E-04	1.08E-03	3.39E-04	4.77E-04	5.21E-03	1.32E-03	6.03E-03
	March	3.49E-05	1.96E-04	1.04E-03	3.26E-04	4.59E-04	5.00E-03	1.27E-03	5.79E-03

	April	4.00E-05	2.25E-04	1.19E-03	3.74E-04	5.23E-04	5.74E-03	1.46E-03	6.64E-03
Cr	Dec	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Jan	2.94E-07	4.53E-09	3.63E-06	5.48E-07	2.11E-09	3.51E-06	3.93E-06	4.06E-06
	Feb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	March	7.44E-06	1.15E-07	9.21E-05	1.39E-05	5.35E-08	8.89E-05	9.96E-05	1.03E-04
	April	9.78E-08	1.51E-09	1.21E-06	1.83E-07	7.04E-10	1.17E-06	1.31E-06	1.35E-06
As	Dec	4.97E-03	7.28E-07	3.00E-03	9.27E-03	3.40E-07	2.90E-03	7.97E-03	1.22E-02
	Jan	6.36E-03	9.32E-07	3.84E-03	1.19E-02	4.35E-07	3.71E-03	1.02E-02	1.56E-02
	Feb	7.53E-03	1.10E-06	4.55E-03	1.41E-02	5.15E-07	4.39E-03	1.21E-02	1.85E-02
	March	2.94E-03	4.30E-07	1.77E-03	5.48E-03	2.01E-07	1.71E-03	4.71E-03	7.19E-03
	April	7.83E-03	1.15E-06	4.73E-03	1.46E-02	5.35E-07	4.57E-03	1.26E-02	1.92E-02
Hg	Dec	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Jan	1.14E-04	5.88E-08	4.04E-04	1.06E-03	1.38E-07	1.95E-03	5.18E-04	3.01E-03
	Feb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	March	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	April	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pb	Dec	3.86E-04	5.64E-08	6.37E-04	7.20E-04	2.63E-08	6.15E-04	1.02E-03	1.34E-03
	Jan	6.98E-04	1.02E-07	1.15E-03	1.30E-03	4.76E-08	1.11E-03	1.85E-03	2.42E-03
	Feb	3.15E-04	4.60E-08	5.19E-04	5.87E-04	2.15E-08	5.01E-04	8.34E-04	1.09E-03
	March	2.10E-04	3.07E-08	3.46E-04	3.91E-04	1.43E-08	3.34E-04	5.56E-04	7.26E-04
	April	3.02E-04	4.41E-08	4.99E-04	5.64E-04	2.06E-08	4.81E-04	8.00E-04	1.04E-03
Mn	Dec	4.83E-04	2.29E-04	2.99E-03	4.50E-03	5.34E-04	1.45E-02	3.70E-03	1.95E-02
	Jan	3.76E-04	1.78E-04	2.33E-03	3.52E-03	4.16E-04	1.13E-02	2.89E-03	1.52E-02
	Feb	2.52E-04	1.20E-04	1.57E-03	2.37E-03	2.79E-04	7.55E-03	1.94E-03	1.02E-02
	March	4.72E-04	2.23E-04	2.92E-03	4.39E-03	5.20E-04	1.41E-02	3.61E-03	1.90E-02
	April	3.63E-04	1.71E-04	2.24E-03	3.39E-03	4.00E-04	1.08E-02	2.78E-03	1.46E-02
Ni	Dec	2.03E-04	2.90E-08	1.86E-04	3.79E-04	1.35E-08	1.80E-04	3.90E-04	5.59E-04
	Jan	9.17E-05	1.31E-08	8.41E-05	1.71E-04	6.11E-09	8.12E-05	1.76E-04	2.52E-04
	Feb	1.54E-05	2.20E-09	1.41E-05	2.88E-05	1.03E-09	1.36E-05	2.95E-05	4.24E-05
	March	3.38E-05	4.82E-09	3.10E-05	6.30E-05	2.25E-09	2.99E-05	6.47E-05	9.29E-05
	April	2.20E-06	3.14E-10	2.02E-06	4.11E-06	1.47E-10	1.95E-06	4.22E-06	6.06E-06

NA: Indicates that reference doses were not available for calculation; „0” means the detectable concentration is zero; Industrial road = Enugu/PH express road.

Table 9. Non-carcinogenic health risks assessment of soil for the selected elements at Agbani road.

SOIL	Samples	ADULT			CHILDREN			HI = \sum HQ	
		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL	INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL		
Elements (mg/kg)	Months	HQ _{ING}	HQ _{INH}	HQ _{DERM}	HQ _{ING}	HQ _{INH}	HQ _{DERM}	ADULT	CHILD
Cu	Dec	3.45E-04	5.02E-08	2.84E-04	3.20E-03	1.17E-07	1.38E-03	6.29E-04	4.58E-03
	Jan	4.03E-04	5.87E-08	3.32E-04	3.73E-03	1.37E-07	1.60E-03	7.34E-04	5.33E-03
	Feb	1.77E-04	2.59E-08	1.46E-04	1.65E-03	6.04E-08	7.04E-04	3.23E-04	2.35E-03
	March	2.35E-04	3.43E-08	1.93E-04	2.19E-03	8.01E-08	9.33E-04	4.28E-04	3.12E-03
	April	1.25E-04	1.83E-08	1.03E-04	1.17E-03	4.28E-08	4.98E-04	2.28E-04	1.67E-03
Fe	Dec	3.50E-05	1.96E-04	1.04E-03	3.26E-04	4.59E-04	5.01E-03	1.27E-03	5.80E-03
	Jan	3.81E-05	2.14E-04	1.13E-03	3.56E-04	4.95E-04	5.47E-03	1.39E-03	6.32E-03
	Feb	3.08E-05	1.74E-04	9.19E-04	2.88E-04	4.05E-04	4.43E-03	1.12E-03	5.12E-03
	March	3.18E-05	1.79E-04	9.44E-04	2.96E-04	4.17E-04	4.56E-03	1.15E-03	5.27E-03
	April	2.61E-05	1.46E-04	7.74E-04	2.43E-04	3.41E-04	3.74E-03	9.47E-04	4.33E-03
Cr	Dec	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Jan	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Feb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	March	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	April	1.80E-05	2.78E-07	2.23E-04	3.36E-05	1.30E-07	2.15E-04	2.41E-04	2.49E-04
As	Dec	6.12E-03	8.96E-07	3.69E-03	1.14E-02	4.18E-07	3.57E-03	9.81E-03	1.50E-02
	Jan	6.09E-03	8.93E-07	3.68E-03	1.14E-02	4.17E-07	3.55E-03	9.77E-03	1.49E-02
	Feb	5.38E-03	7.89E-07	3.25E-03	1.00E-02	3.68E-07	3.14E-03	8.63E-03	1.32E-02
	March	6.16E-03	9.04E-07	3.72E-03	1.15E-02	4.22E-07	3.60E-03	9.89E-03	1.51E-02
	April	6.04E-03	8.86E-07	3.65E-03	1.13E-02	4.13E-07	3.52E-03	9.69E-03	1.48E-02

Hg	Dec	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Jan	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Feb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	March	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	April	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pb	Dec	7.61E-04	1.11E-07	1.26E-03	1.42E-03	5.19E-08	1.21E-03	2.02E-03	2.63E-03
	Jan	6.50E-04	9.50E-08	1.07E-03	1.21E-03	4.44E-08	1.04E-03	1.72E-03	2.25E-03
	Feb	3.48E-04	5.09E-08	5.75E-04	6.50E-04	2.38E-08	5.55E-04	9.23E-04	1.20E-03
	March	4.32E-04	6.32E-08	7.13E-04	8.06E-04	2.95E-08	6.89E-04	1.15E-03	1.49E-03
	April	6.77E-04	9.90E-08	1.12E-03	1.26E-03	4.62E-08	1.08E-03	1.80E-03	2.34E-03
Mn	Dec	3.78E-04	1.79E-04	2.34E-03	3.54E-03	4.18E-04	1.13E-02	2.90E-03	1.53E-02
	Jan	5.11E-04	2.41E-04	3.16E-03	4.76E-03	5.64E-04	1.53E-02	3.92E-03	2.06E-02
	Feb	2.93E-04	1.39E-04	1.82E-03	2.74E-03	3.24E-04	8.80E-03	2.25E-03	1.19E-02
	March	1.84E-04	8.67E-05	1.14E-03	1.72E-03	2.03E-04	5.49E-03	1.41E-03	7.41E-03
	April	4.09E-04	1.93E-04	2.53E-03	3.80E-03	4.50E-04	1.22E-02	3.13E-03	1.64E-02
Ni	Dec	1.45E-04	2.07E-08	1.33E-04	2.71E-04	9.66E-09	1.28E-04	2.78E-04	3.99E-04
	Jan	6.02E-05	8.59E-09	5.52E-05	1.12E-04	4.01E-09	5.33E-05	1.15E-04	1.66E-04
	Feb	7.34E-06	1.05E-09	6.73E-06	1.37E-05	4.89E-10	6.50E-06	1.41E-05	2.02E-05
	March	4.40E-05	6.29E-09	4.04E-05	8.22E-05	2.93E-09	3.90E-05	8.44E-05	1.21E-04
	April	4.22E-05	6.02E-09	3.87E-05	7.88E-05	2.81E-09	3.74E-05	8.09E-05	1.16E-04

NA: Indicates that reference doses were not available for calculation; „0” means the detectable concentration is zero; Commercial road = Agbani road.

Table 10. Non-carcinogenic health risks assessment of soil for the selected elements at Ogui road.

SOIL	Samples	ADULT			CHILDREN			HI = \sum HQ	
		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL	INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL		
Elements (mg/kg)	Months	HQ _{ING}	HQ _{INH}	HQ _{DERM}	HQ _{ING}	HQ _{INH}	HQ _{DERM}	ADULT	CHILD

Cu	Dec	1.90E-04	2.79E-08	1.57E-04	1.77E-03	6.47E-08	7.56E-04	3.46E-04	2.53E-03
	Jan	1.23E-04	1.80E-08	1.02E-04	1.15E-03	4.20E-08	4.91E-04	2.25E-04	1.64E-03
	Feb	1.59E-04	2.32E-08	1.31E-04	1.48E-03	5.40E-08	6.31E-04	2.89E-04	2.11E-03
	March	1.07E-04	1.56E-08	8.83E-05	9.98E-04	3.66E-08	4.27E-04	1.95E-04	1.42E-03
	April	1.58E-04	2.31E-08	1.30E-04	1.47E-03	5.37E-08	6.28E-04	2.88E-04	2.10E-03
Fe	Dec	2.81E-05	1.58E-04	8.34E-04	2.62E-04	3.68E-04	4.03E-03	1.02E-03	4.66E-03
	Jan	2.57E-05	1.45E-04	7.64E-04	2.40E-04	3.37E-04	3.69E-03	9.35E-04	4.26E-03
	Feb	2.63E-05	1.48E-04	7.81E-04	2.45E-04	3.44E-04	3.77E-03	9.55E-04	4.36E-03
	March	3.08E-05	1.74E-04	9.19E-04	2.88E-04	4.05E-04	4.44E-03	1.12E-03	5.14E-03
	April	2.25E-05	1.26E-04	6.69E-04	2.11E-04	2.95E-04	3.23E-03	8.17E-04	3.73E-03
Cr	Dec	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Jan	1.96E-07	3.02E-09	2.42E-06	3.65E-07	1.41E-09	2.34E-06	2.62E-06	2.71E-06
	Feb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	March	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	April	1.04E-05	1.60E-07	1.28E-04	1.94E-05	7.47E-08	1.24E-04	1.39E-04	1.43E-04
As	Dec	6.12E-03	8.96E-07	3.69E-03	1.14E-02	4.18E-07	3.57E-03	9.81E-03	1.50E-02
	Jan	4.67E-03	6.85E-07	2.82E-03	8.72E-03	3.20E-07	2.72E-03	7.50E-03	1.14E-02
	Feb	7.24E-03	1.06E-06	4.37E-03	1.35E-02	4.95E-07	4.22E-03	1.16E-02	1.77E-02
	March	6.31E-03	9.25E-07	3.81E-03	1.18E-02	4.32E-07	3.68E-03	1.01E-02	1.55E-02
	April	2.89E-03	4.23E-07	1.74E-03	5.39E-03	1.97E-07	1.68E-03	4.63E-03	7.07E-03
Hg	Dec	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Jan	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Feb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	March	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	April	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pb	Dec	1.76E-04	2.58E-08	2.91E-04	3.29E-04	1.20E-08	2.81E-04	4.67E-04	6.10E-04
	Jan	1.17E-04	1.72E-08	1.94E-04	2.19E-04	8.01E-09	1.87E-04	3.11E-04	4.06E-04
	Feb	2.31E-04	3.37E-08	3.81E-04	4.31E-04	1.57E-08	3.68E-04	6.11E-04	7.98E-04
	March	2.18E-04	3.19E-08	3.60E-04	4.07E-04	1.49E-08	3.48E-04	5.78E-04	7.55E-04
	April	9.64E-05	1.41E-08	1.59E-04	1.80E-04	6.58E-09	1.54E-04	2.56E-04	3.34E-04
Mn	Dec	6.48E-04	3.06E-04	4.01E-03	6.04E-03	7.13E-04	1.93E-02	4.96E-03	2.61E-02

	Jan	2.91E-04	1.37E-04	1.80E-03	2.72E-03	3.20E-04	8.64E-03	2.23E-03	1.17E-02
	Feb	4.04E-04	1.91E-04	2.51E-03	3.78E-03	4.46E-04	1.21E-02	3.10E-03	1.63E-02
	March	4.76E-04	2.26E-04	2.96E-03	4.46E-03	5.27E-04	1.43E-02	3.66E-03	1.93E-02
	April	3.33E-04	1.58E-04	2.06E-03	3.11E-03	3.68E-04	9.95E-03	2.55E-03	1.34E-02
Ni	Dec	4.40E-05	6.29E-09	4.04E-05	8.22E-05	2.93E-09	3.90E-05	8.44E-05	1.21E-04
	Jan	4.40E-05	6.29E-09	4.04E-05	8.22E-05	2.93E-09	3.90E-05	8.44E-05	1.21E-04
	Feb	7.34E-07	1.05E-10	6.73E-07	1.37E-06	4.89E-11	6.50E-07	1.41E-06	2.02E-06
	March	3.63E-05	5.19E-09	3.33E-05	6.78E-05	2.42E-09	3.22E-05	6.97E-05	1.00E-04
	April	1.32E-05	1.89E-09	1.21E-05	2.47E-05	8.80E-10	1.17E-05	2.53E-05	3.64E-05

NA: Indicates that reference doses were not available for calculation; „0” means the detectable concentration is zero; Residential road = ogui road.

The results in Tables 8, 9 and 10 showed the HQ values for adults and children via ingestion, dermal contact and inhalation pathways were found to be less than one ($HQ < 1$) which indicates no non-carcinogenic risks for adults and children in the three urban roads. Apparently, the HI values for Cr, As, Ni, Cu, Hg, Fe, Pb, Mn are all lower than the safe level ($HI < 1$) for all sampling sites, indicating that there is no significant health risk of non-carcinogenic effect of these heavy metals in the study roads for adults and children. However, in terms of the two population groups, the non-carcinogenic health risks for children were higher than the risks for adults, suggesting that children faced more potential harmful health risks from the heavy metals in the urban roadside soils. The carcinogenic risks for As, Cr, Pb, and Ni were estimated. According to Fryer et al. (2006) risks surpassing 1×10^{-4} are viewed as unacceptable, whereas risks below 1×10^{-6} are not considered to pose significant health effects and risks lying in the range of $10^{-6} - 10^{-4}$ are generally regarded as tolerable to some degree. As shown in Tables 11, 12 and 13, the CR values for children were higher than adults. For both children and adults, the CR values followed the order of $Ni > As > Cr > Pb$. Of the four heavy metals, Cr, and Pb were less than 10^{-6} . And the CR values of Ni and As for children and adults were 1.08×10^{-5} and 1.17×10^{-5} , and 2.08×10^{-6} and 3.18×10^{-6} respectively, which were between 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} . Thus, carcinogenic risk from exposure to these metals is negligible in the three urban roadside soils studied. It was discovered that children had higher carcinogenic risks than adults in the three exposure pathways considered, indicating that children are more vulnerable to health implication heavy metals in the roadside soil. The children frequently engaged in hand-to-mouth activities and various outdoor plays. They also experience high respiration rate per unit body weight hence breathing more deeply into lung dust containing heavy metals with systematic toxicity and health risks. The values of HI indices were the highest in most congested traffic roads, and they were as follows: in Enugu/PH express road (HI 2.97 for children and 0.319 for adults), in Agbani road (HI 2.88 for children and 0.309 for adults) and in Ogui new layout road (HI 2.34 for children and 0.25 for adults). In this study, the sampling of urban roadside soil was mainly distributed to the three main traffic roads of Enugu city and non-carcinogenic HIs of eight heavy metals (Cr, As, Ni, Cu, Hg, Fe, Pb and Mn) for children and adults were all lower than 1 thereby posing no health hazard.

Table 11. Cancer risk (CR) values for heavy metals in soil for adults and children from Enugu/PH express road.

ADI and cancer risk (CR) values									
SOIL	Samples	ADULT			CHILDREN			TCR	
		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL	INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL		
Elements (mg/kg)	Months	CR _{ING}	CR _{INH}	CR _{DERM}	CR _{ING}	CR _{INH}	CR _{DERM}	ADULT	CHILD
Cr	Dec	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	Jan	4.40E-10	5.44E-12	4.36E-09	8.22E-10	2.54E-12	4.21E-09	4.81E-09	5.04E-09
	Feb	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	March	1.12E-08	1.38E-10	1.11E-07	2.08E-08	6.43E-11	1.07E-07	1.22E-07	1.28E-07
	April	1.47E-10	1.81E-12	1.45E-09	2.74E-10	8.46E-13	1.40E-09	1.60E-09	1.68E-09
As	Dec	2.23E-06	9.42E-13	1.35E-06	4.17E-06	4.40E-13	1.30E-06	3.58E-06	5.48E-06
	Jan	2.86E-06	1.21E-12	1.73E-06	5.34E-06	5.63E-13	1.67E-06	4.59E-06	7.01E-06
	Feb	3.39E-06	1.43E-12	2.05E-06	6.33E-06	6.67E-13	1.98E-06	5.44E-06	8.31E-06
	March	1.32E-06	5.57E-13	7.98E-07	2.47E-06	2.60E-13	7.71E-07	2.12E-06	3.24E-06
	April	3.52E-06	1.48E-12	2.13E-06	6.58E-06	6.93E-13	2.06E-06	5.65E-06	8.63E-06
Pb	Dec	1.15E-08	8.34E-12	NA	2.14E-08	3.89E-12	NA	1.15E-08	2.14E-08
	Jan	2.08E-08	1.51E-11	NA	3.88E-08	7.04E-12	NA	2.08E-08	3.88E-08
	Feb	9.36E-09	6.80E-12	NA	1.75E-08	3.17E-12	NA	9.36E-09	1.75E-08
	March	6.24E-09	4.53E-12	NA	1.16E-08	2.12E-12	NA	6.24E-09	1.16E-08
	April	8.98E-09	6.53E-12	NA	1.68E-08	3.05E-12	NA	8.98E-09	1.68E-08
Ni	Dec	6.91E-06	5.02E-10	4.28E-05	1.29E-05	2.34E-10	4.13E-05	4.97E-05	5.42E-05
	Jan	3.12E-06	2.27E-10	1.93E-05	5.82E-06	1.06E-10	1.86E-05	2.24E-05	2.45E-05
	Feb	5.24E-07	3.81E-11	3.24E-06	9.78E-07	1.78E-11	3.13E-06	3.77E-06	4.11E-06
	March	1.15E-06	8.34E-11	7.11E-06	2.14E-06	3.89E-11	6.86E-06	8.25E-06	9.00E-06
	April	7.49E-08	5.44E-12	4.63E-07	1.40E-07	2.54E-12	4.47E-07	5.38E-07	5.87E-07

NA: Indicates that dermal slope factor of Pb were not available for calculation; „0” means the detectable concentration is zero.

Table 12. Cancer risk (CR) values for heavy metals in soil for adults and children from Agbani road.

ADI and cancer risk (CR) values									
SOIL	Samples	ADULT			CHILDREN			TCR	
		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL	INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL		
Elements (mg/kg)	Months	CR _{ING}	CR _{INH}	CR _{DERM}	CR _{ING}	CR _{INH}	CR _{DERM}	ADULT	CHILD
Cr	Dec	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	Jan	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	Feb	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	March	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	April	2.70E-08	3.34E-10	2.68E-07	5.04E-08	1.56E-10	2.58E-07	2.95E-07	3.09E-07
As	Dec	2.75E-06	1.16E-12	1.66E-06	5.14E-06	5.41E-13	1.61E-06	4.41E-06	6.74E-06
	Jan	2.74E-06	1.16E-12	1.66E-06	5.12E-06	5.39E-13	1.60E-06	4.40E-06	6.72E-06
	Feb	2.42E-06	1.02E-12	1.46E-06	4.52E-06	4.76E-13	1.41E-06	3.89E-06	5.93E-06
	March	2.77E-06	1.17E-12	1.68E-06	5.18E-06	5.46E-13	1.62E-06	4.45E-06	6.80E-06
	April	2.72E-06	1.15E-12	1.64E-06	5.08E-06	5.35E-13	1.59E-06	4.36E-06	6.66E-06
Pb	Dec	2.26E-08	1.65E-11	NA	4.23E-08	7.68E-12	NA	2.26E-08	4.23E-08
	Jan	1.93E-08	1.41E-11	NA	3.61E-08	6.56E-12	NA	1.93E-08	3.61E-08
	Feb	1.04E-08	7.52E-12	NA	1.93E-08	3.51E-12	NA	1.04E-08	1.93E-08
	March	1.28E-08	9.34E-12	NA	2.40E-08	4.36E-12	NA	1.28E-08	2.40E-08
	April	2.01E-08	1.46E-11	NA	3.76E-08	6.83E-12	NA	2.01E-08	3.76E-08
Ni	Dec	4.93E-06	3.58E-10	3.05E-05	9.20E-06	1.67E-10	2.95E-05	3.54E-05	3.87E-05
	Jan	2.05E-06	1.49E-10	1.27E-05	3.82E-06	6.94E-11	1.22E-05	1.47E-05	1.61E-05
	Feb	2.50E-07	1.81E-11	1.54E-06	4.66E-07	8.46E-12	1.49E-06	1.79E-06	1.96E-06
	March	1.50E-06	1.09E-10	9.27E-06	2.79E-06	5.08E-11	8.95E-06	1.08E-05	1.17E-05
	April	1.43E-06	1.04E-10	8.88E-06	2.68E-06	4.87E-11	8.58E-06	1.03E-05	1.13E-05

NA: Indicates that dermal slope factor of Pb were not available for calculation; „0” means the detectable concentration is zero.

Table 13. Cancer risk (CR) values for heavy metals in soil for adults and children for from Ogui road.

ADI and cancer risk (CR) values									
SOIL	Samples	ADULT			CHILDREN			TCR	
		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL	INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL		
Elements (mg/kg)	Months	CR _{ING}	CR _{INH}	CR _{DERM}	CR _{ING}	CR _{INH}	CR _{DERM}	ADULT	CHILD
Cr	Dec	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	Jan	2.94E-10	3.63E-12	2.91E-09	5.48E-10	1.69E-12	2.81E-09	3.21E-09	3.36E-09
	Feb	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	March	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
	April	1.56E-08	1.92E-10	1.54E-07	2.90E-08	8.97E-11	1.49E-07	1.70E-07	1.78E-07
As	Dec	2.75E-06	1.16E-12	1.66E-06	5.14E-06	5.41E-13	1.61E-06	4.41E-06	6.74E-06
	Jan	2.10E-06	8.86E-13	1.27E-06	3.92E-06	4.14E-13	1.23E-06	3.37E-06	5.15E-06
	Feb	3.26E-06	1.37E-12	1.97E-06	6.08E-06	6.41E-13	1.90E-06	5.23E-06	7.98E-06
	March	2.84E-06	1.20E-12	1.72E-06	5.30E-06	5.59E-13	1.66E-06	4.56E-06	6.96E-06
	April	1.30E-06	5.48E-13	7.85E-07	2.42E-06	2.56E-13	7.58E-07	2.08E-06	3.18E-06
Pb	Dec	5.24E-09	3.81E-12	NA	9.78E-09	1.78E-12	NA	5.24E-09	9.78E-09
	Jan	3.49E-09	2.54E-12	NA	6.52E-09	1.18E-12	NA	3.49E-09	6.52E-09
	Feb	6.86E-09	4.99E-12	NA	1.28E-08	2.33E-12	NA	6.86E-09	1.28E-08
	March	6.49E-09	4.71E-12	NA	1.21E-08	2.20E-12	NA	6.49E-09	1.21E-08
	April	2.87E-09	2.09E-12	NA	5.36E-09	9.73E-13	NA	2.87E-09	5.36E-09
Ni	Dec	1.50E-06	1.09E-10	9.27E-06	2.79E-06	5.08E-11	8.95E-06	1.08E-05	1.17E-05
	Jan	1.50E-06	1.09E-10	9.27E-06	2.79E-06	5.08E-11	8.95E-06	1.08E-05	1.17E-05
	Feb	2.50E-08	1.81E-12	1.54E-07	4.66E-08	8.46E-13	1.49E-07	1.79E-07	1.96E-07
	March	1.24E-06	8.97E-11	7.65E-06	2.31E-06	4.19E-11	7.38E-06	8.88E-06	9.69E-06
	April	4.49E-07	3.26E-11	2.78E-06	8.38E-07	1.52E-11	2.68E-06	3.23E-06	3.52E-06

NA: Indicates that dermal slope factor of Pb were not available for calculation; „0” means the detectable concentration is zero.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Roadside soils can act as sinks for traffic-related heavy metals potentially affecting health through direct exposure. This study evaluated the concentrations and potential health risks of selected heavy metals (Pb, Mn, Ni, Cu, Cr, As, Hg and Fe) in surface soils from three major urban roads in Enugu State, Nigeria. The highest concentration was recorded for Fe while the lowest amount was for Hg and Cr. Pollution indices fell within uncontaminated to moderately contaminated ranges. Hazard Quotients for all the heavy metals and exposure pathways were < 1 and the cumulative Hazard Index for both adults and children were also < 1 , which shows no significant non-carcinogenic health risk. Cancer risk values for Cr, As, Pb and Ni were within the acceptable risk range (10^{-6} - 10^{-4}), indicating negligible carcinogenic risk. Therefore, the results indicate that heavy metal concentrations in soils along the three urban roads on Enugu are generally within the safe limits and non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic assessments show no significant health threat for both adult and children. Nevertheless, periodic monitoring is recommended to ensure that increase traffic and urbanization do not elevate future exposure risks.

References

- [1] Abechi, E.S., Okunola, O.J. Zubairu, S.M.J. Usman AA and Apene E. (2010). Evaluation of heavy metals in roadside soils of major streets in Jos metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Chemistry and Ecotoxicology*, 2(6): 98-102
- [2] Adimalla, N. and Wang, H. (2018). Distribution, contamination, and health risk assessment of heavy metals in surface soils from northern Telangana, India. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 11(21), 684. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-018-4028-y>
- [3] Alexander, P. (2015). Assessment of heavy metals in roadside surface soil and vegetation along Mubi-Michika road in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Int. J. Appl Sci. Biotechnology*, 3(3):545-551
- [4] Chen, H., Kwong, J.C., Copes, R., Tu, K., Villeneuve, P.J., van Donkelaar, A. and Burnett, R.T. (2017). Living near major roads and the incidence of dementia, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis: a population-based cohort study. *Lancet*, 389(10070): 718–726
- [5] Dakane, A. (2012). *Bioaccessibility of Metals in Toronto City Parks*, Doctoral dissertation, Royal Roads University, Victoria, British Columbia. pp. 440-460
- [6] Daud M., Wasim M., Khalid N., Zaidi J.H. and Iqbal J. (2009). Assessment of elemental pollution in soil of Islamabad city using instrumental neutron activation analysis and atomic absorption spectrometry techniques. *Radiochimica Acta, International Journal for Chemical Aspects of Nuclear Science and Technology*, 97(2), 117-121
- [7] DPR (2002). Environmental guidelines and Standards for the petroleum industries in Nigeria Department of Petroleum Resources, Ministry of Petroleum and Mineral Resources, Abuja, Nigeria.

- [8] Fryer, P., Gharib, J., Ross, K., Savov, I. and Mottl, M. J. (2006). Variability in Serpentinite Mudflow Mechanisms and Sources: ODP Drilling Results on Mariana Forearc Seamounts. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, 7(8): 08014
- [9] Gary, D.C. (2004). Analytical Chemistry 6th Edition. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., Washington. Pp. 21-113
- [10] Huu, H. H., Rudy S. and An Van Damme. (2010). Distribution and contamination status of heavy metals in estuarine sediments near Cau Ong harbor, Ha Long Bay, Vietnam. *Geology Belgica*, 13(1-2): 37-47
- [11] Keshav Krishna, A. and Rama Mohan, K. (2016). Distribution, correlation, ecological and health risk assessment of heavy metal contamination in surface soils around an industrial area, Hyderabad, India. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 75(5), 411
- [12] Khademi, H., Gabarro'n, M., Abbaspour, A., Marti'nez-Marti' - nez, S., Faz, A. and Acosta, J. A. (2019). Environmental impact assessment of industrial activities on heavy metals distribution in street dust and soil. *Chemosphere*, 217, 695–705
- [13] Khare, P. and Baruah, B.P. (2010). Elemental characterization and source identification of PM2.5 using multivariate analysis at the suburban site of North-East India. *Atmos. Res.* 98 (1), 148e162
- [14] Lacatusu, R. (2000). Appraising levels of soil contamination and pollution with heavy metals. In: Heinike H. J., Eckrelman W., Thomasson A. J, Jones R. J. A, Montanarella L. and Buckley B. (eds) Land information system for planning the sustainable use of land resources. *European soil bureau. Research report no 4*. Office for Official Publication of the European Communities, Luxembourg. 393–402
- [15] Lu, X., Wang, L. and Lei, K. (2009). Contamination assessment of copper, lead, zinc, manganese and nickel in street dust of Baoji, NW China, *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 161: 1058–1062
- [16] Muller, G. (1969). Index of geo-accumulation in sediments of the Rhine River. *Geo. J.* 2(3): 108-118
- [17] Okoye, T.O. (1975). Enugu, in GEK Ofomata (ed) Nigeria in Maps: Eastern States Ethope Publishing House Benin City Nigeria.
- [18] Poggio, L., Vrščaj, B., Hepperle, E., Schulin, R. and Marsan, F.A. (2008). Introducing a method of human health risk evaluation for planning and soil quality management of heavy metal-polluted soils – An example from Grugliasco (Italy). *Landsc. Urban Plan*, 88, 64–72
- [19] Praveena, S. M., Pradhan, B. and Ismail, S. N. S. (2015). Spatial assessment of heavy metals in surface soil from Klang District (Malaysia): An example from a tropical environment. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 21(7), 1980–2003. doi:10.1080/ 10807039.2015.1017872
- [20] Radojevic, M. and Bashkin, V. (2006). Practical environmental analysis. *Royal Society of Chemistry*, ISBN: 978-1-78262-548-3. <https://doi.org/10.1039/9781847552662>
- [21] Suresh, G., Ramasamy, V., Sundarrajan, M. and Paramasivam, K. (2015). Spatial and vertical distributions of heavy metals and their potential toxicity levels in various beach

- sediments from highbackground-radiation area, Kerala, India. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 91(1), 389–400
- [22] Thomilson, D.C., Wilson, D.J., Harris, C.R. and Jeffrey, D.W. (1980). Problems in the assessment of heavy metal levels in estuaries and the formation of a pollution index. *Helgoländer Meeresuntersuchungen*, 33(1-4): 566-575
- [23] USEPA. (2009). Risk Assessment Guidance for Superfund Volume I: human Health Evaluation Manual (Part F, Supplemental Guidance for Inhalation Risk Assessment). Washington (D.C): Office of Superfund Remediation and Technology Innovation
- [24] USEPA. (2002). Supplemental guidance for developing soil screening levels for superfund sites. Washington, DC: U. S. Environmental Protection Agency, Office of Emergency and Remedial Response.
- [25] Wang, G., Zeng, C., Zhang, F., Zhang, Y., Scott, C. and Yan, X. (2017). Traffic-related trace elements in soils along six highway segments on the Tibetan Plateau: Influence factors and spatial variation. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 581-582, 811-821
- [26] Wei, B. and Yang, L. (2010). A review of heavy metal contaminations in urban soils, urban road dusts and agricultural soils from China. *Microchem J* 94(2), 99–107
- [27] Zhao, K., Fu, W., Qiu, Q., Ye, Z., Li, Y. and Tunney, H. (2019). Spatial patterns of potentially hazardous metals in paddy soils in a typical electrical waste dismantling area and their pollution characteristics. *Geoderma*, 337, 453–462